

Codebook				
Themes	Subthemes	Codes	Quotes	Citations
Current use of EPRs by health professionals and patients	Lack of completeness and interoperability of information between different entities.	Current Problem Completeness Data Integration Remote locations	<p>PS1 "There's never this complete record, because I don't know what the other professional does. Basically, there are many doctors who don't fill out the medical records properly."</p> <p>PS1 "We don't have access to the patient's consultation records... So none of this is integrated. I worked at PSE in Pindoretama where they had their internal system, but it only served a single health center. I couldn't see patient progress from other centers in the region or from specialists."</p> <p>PS1 "We have this difficulty in forwarding data to another unit, precisely because there is no integrated online system, and it makes communication very difficult"</p> <p>IS1 "For example, if I have a patient in primary care, they are registered in my unit, but if they are being followed by CAPES, these are services from the same municipality, in the same context, but we don't have access. We don't have information from that patient's medical records from the unit, what we often know is from some prescription that the patient brings, information given by the patient themselves, in this case"</p> <p>PS2 "There is, for example, if we transfer a patient, or if we treat a patient from another hospital, we can request information provided by them, or when there is, for example, a referral then the report comes or even if the patient requests a copy of the medical record because it is a patient's document so you can request a copy of the entire medical record if you want"</p>	<p>1:26 ¶ 73 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:3 ¶ 5 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:5 ¶ 7 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:7 ¶ 21 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>2:9 ¶ 31 in Transcription - Group2</p>
	Importance of recording medical data to health professionals.	Communication Documentation	<p>PS2 "We... are always being trained to write everything we do with patients, everything that we, for example, request consultation for any professional, both medical and from other areas. So this communication, from what I see, happens a lot in writing in terms of consultation notes"</p> <p>IS1 "We in healthcare, when we're on duty in the health service, the way we prove our service that we're doing with the patient is through notation, through recording."</p>	<p>2:1 ¶ 13 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>1:52 ¶ 193 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Access control by the patients to health professionals.	Communication Current Problem Control Access	<p>PS2 "We have access to data, for example, what other doctors write in medical records, both physical when printed and in systems"</p> <p>LM2 "We usually pass it on by phone, calling responsible nursing units and we pass it to nurses and they pass it to doctors. It's uncommon that we also leave the laboratory itself and go after the patient's records to understand the cause"</p> <p>PS1 "privacy there is no privacy for those who work in the hospital"</p> <p>LM1 "What we do is request medical consultation. So we contact the doctor responsible for the patient, or the nurse who's at the post at the moment and request this information, but having access to the medical record ourselves, no."</p>	<p>2:2 ¶ 13 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>2:4 ¶ 18 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>1:40 ¶ 127 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:6 ¶ 12 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Flow and hierarchy of activities among health professionals to the patient records.	Coordination Cooperation	<p>IS2 "context where the doctor prescribes information from doctor to doctor in prescriptions and medical progress notes and also from doctor to nurse we check the progress notes and after prescribed we schedule and act according to the prescription throughout the day and there may be changes where the doctor makes the change and communicates to the nurse to schedule so the technician then executes any medication that should be administered or procedure"</p> <p>IS2 "professional has access to change a certain issue within the medical record; the doctor makes the prescription, a nurse schedules it."</p>	<p>2:7 ¶ 24 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>2:6 ¶ 24 in Transcription - Group2</p>
	Current storage and management of records by patients.	Current Problems Control Access Record Management	<p>Patient2 "I just store it, I don't do very elaborate management, so I have the vaccination card document for vaccines, but for exams, hospitalization these things... For example, exams I keep for a while, then I discard"</p> <p>Patient1 "To this day I still keep the envelope because wherever I go regarding health I keep taking this."</p>	<p>2:14 ¶ 50 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>1:8 ¶ 26 in Transcription - Group1</p>
3C Collaboration Model	Sharing and viewing patient information by professionals.	Communication Collaboration Cooperation	<p>IS1 "helps a lot with communication. Because, unfortunately, people, health professionals still can't work on this interprofessionalism issue, which is urgent, always has been, I believe. And because we don't have this, because we don't have this integration, just being able to view the information prescribed by another doctor, or my fellow nurse, sometimes Mediator, due to the rush, we can't pass all information from one shift to another, for example."</p> <p>PS2 "Definitely. And maybe even in the way you ask questions for us to fill out, there's room to improve the quality of anamnesis especially depending on the context, for example, in an emergency, or sometimes during a shift, the professional is tired, they might not ask everything. So if you put semi-structured anamnesis, it makes it much easier, you see. And then when passing to another professional, everything organized facilitates investigation. That's how I see it."</p> <p>PS2 "regarding doctor's handwriting, obviously. Often we don't understand what others write. So electronic medical records already help because it's typed"</p> <p>IS1 "This matter of having everything electronic greatly facilitates reading and understanding"</p> <p>LM1 "The other laboratory usually doesn't normally have the patient's history from my laboratory. This will give an improvement. Although each laboratory uses different methodologies for the same exam, this at least gives direction to the analyst when they're going to report the exam"</p> <p>PS1 "because then I know what the other professional is thinking"</p> <p>PS1 "if this use becomes widespread, and doctors are conscious, I speak for my area, of putting the data properly in this system, it would become much easier indeed, and we wouldn't lose patient information."</p>	<p>1:54 ¶ 193 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>2:17 ¶ 73 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>2:22 ¶ 106 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>1:25 ¶ 68 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:35 ¶ 91 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:16 ¶ 60 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:27 ¶ 73 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Awareness of health professionals and interprofessionalism among them.	Collaboration Cooperation Communication Professional Engagement	<p>PS1 "if this use becomes widespread, and doctors are conscious, I speak for my area, of putting the data properly in this system, it would become much easier indeed, and we wouldn't lose patient information."</p> <p>IS1 "helps a lot with communication. Because, unfortunately, health professionals still can't work on this interprofessionalism issue, which is urgent, always has been, I believe. And because we don't have this, because we don't have this integration, just being able to view the information prescribed by another doctor, or my fellow nurse, sometimes Mediator, due to the rush, we can't pass all information from one shift to another, for example."</p> <p>PS2 "And it helps the team tremendously if this interaction comes with the correct dialogue and in the way we're putting it, this is exceptional in reality."</p>	<p>1:27 ¶ 73 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:54 ¶ 193 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>2:19 ¶ 75 in Transcription - Group2</p>
	Availability of medical records and prevention of information loss about the patient's segment.	Communication Availability	<p>PS1 "I think it serves for us not to lose information about the patient's follow-up."</p> <p>PS1 "If everything is done properly, it's good because of this, we stop losing information, which sometimes the patient doesn't remember, sometimes lost a test or doesn't bring it. We stop losing information and have better follow-up"</p>	<p>1:13 ¶ 51 in Transcription - Group1</p> <p>1:15 ¶ 51 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Changes to the information within the medical record.	Control Access Data Immutability	<p>IS2 "professional has access to change a certain issue within the medical record; the doctor makes the prescription, a nurse schedules it."</p> <p>IS2 "Another point that we need to observe is that there needs to be a context for a correction, so for example, I wrote down a medication, a non-recommended dose, but noticed before the medication was administered, so I leave the record as a cancellation and put the correct prescription below, this is important to have, and another thing, any change that is executed must be linked to the access password credentials of that professional, because then they logged in with their password, they made the change and they are ethically responsible for the modification, so this is the context that I see."</p>	<p>2:6 ¶ 24 in Transcription - Group2</p> <p>2:37 ¶ 200 in Transcription - Group2</p>

	Access and availability of information.	Availability Security	<p>IS1 "So this proposal is interesting so that the patient who has this interest, has this curiosity to always have their information, it's available there" Patient1 "So, regardless of what happens, that will be available to other network members. Even if not accessing it at that time, it's recorded, but access, obviously I'll have to authorize, but that doesn't get lost. So it's extremely good." PS2 "I think it's a mechanism to increase security because they're important data, you can't lose the information, I think in this sense." IS2 "so it would be important that we had a replica in more than one place to not be tied to this, because then we wouldn't have any problem, okay, so in this sense I think it's important the possibility of availability of medical records information remembering these contexts we talked about, that this information can and will leak, of course this might not happen, okay, but it's a situation which will be susceptible, and about losses it's good to remember that today we already lose a lot, because paper has a shelf life, so this digital record is important, because, so much that I've worked in places that I might be wrong, but for example, after 10 years, SUS doesn't have to keep that record on paper anymore, the paper can be eliminated, can go to an archive, so this is... will change when I have this record" LM2 "I understand blockchain very superficially but I believe this is indeed a very good possibility, of having your data in various places and not having the dependency, and not having the record only in one place, and having to redo everything again." IS1 "As the system would go down, as we had to register afterwards in the system, everything that was noted had to be registered."</p>	<p>1:18 ¶ 63 in Transcription - Group1 1:57 ¶ 223 in Transcription - Group1 2:42 ¶ 248 in Transcription - Group2 2:43 ¶ 254 in Transcription - Group2 2:44 ¶ 258 in Transcription - Group2 1:56 ¶ 214 in Transcription - Group1 1:28 ¶ 79 in Transcription - Group1</p>
Practical adoption and enablers of a blockchain-based EPR	Immutability, traceability, and information auditing increase security for all parties.	Immutability Security	<p>LM1 "So, the laboratories will be more cautious, doing, releasing these results, which should be normal. The normal thing is to be already cautious. But, yes, this leaves it written down forever and makes it easier for the patient to access this error." IS1 "Because the record is information and the support for your work." IS1 "It contributes to both parties, not only, once again, not only to the patient but to the professional as well." PS2 "I think it increases patient safety, especially, like, there is no way you can, if that is what I understood, if there is no way to modify a prescription or even some record that we make in the medical record, there would be no way to modify it, which sometimes causes problems, the patient can say that he informed something and it is not recorded, or vice versa, the doctor says that he recorded it and it is not written there, anyway, I think it is in the sense of improving security because you enter with the password, it is saved there, right... I think that's how it is." IS2 "Okay, I think that, like this, on this point of immutability, right, it must be interprofessional; one professional cannot change what was done by another. I cannot change the medical prescription, just like the doctor should not be able to change it, although he can already set the appointment, but whatever I do, he should not be able to change it, okay." Patient2 "I do not know if I understood correctly, but I would particularly like to have my entire history at hand, as it was with the guarantee that nothing was changed and that nothing was modified, that really from the first record to the most recent record all my information is immutable." IS2 "It is important that private institutions audit their medical records every month, including every thirty days, and in public institutions as well, but the audit in public institutions is smaller and sometimes applies to more complex contexts, such as surgeries and transplants, which also fall under this category. Patients are admitted to the ICU, so there is an audit a priori, an audit to verify private payments and so that public institutions receive the incentives and payments determined for the patient. So, private institutions take great advantage of medical records with an incorrect prescription, a prescription out of context, and a prescription that was not written correctly, so it goes back for correction, leaving the initial record. As I said, that's right, and it is changed where, in what concerns the payment part, but always leaving the initial record, so the audit is done internally, then externally if necessary, for example for a patient consultation, it will be determined who will audit the medical record there, so it is important that even that that was changed, right, what was changed, there should be a record of what changed and what it was before, so that the patient can be 100% sure of what was done and also observe what was changed, right." IS1 "It guarantees the patient's safety and the professional's performance. I think the professional's support" PS1 "Is good for the patient's sake and for us to be legally protected, right? So, if you write something in the medical record, it will stay there; you cannot change it later; sometimes, we protect ourselves against the conduct of another doctor, for example."</p>	<p>1:49 ¶ 184 in Transcription - Group1 1:51 ¶ 193 in Transcription - Group1 1:53 ¶ 193 in Transcription - Group1 2:35 ¶ 196 in Transcription - Group2 2:36 ¶ 200 in Transcription - Group2 2:39 ¶ 224 in Transcription - Group2 2:40 ¶ 228 in Transcription - Group2</p>
	Service Quality	Quality	<p>PS2 "For sure. And maybe even in the way you pose questions for us to fill out, there's room to improve the quality of the anamnesis, especially depending on the context. For example, in an emergency, or sometimes during a shift, the professional is tired, they certainly might not ask everything. So if you put a semi-structured anamnesis, that helps a lot, you understand. And then when it passes to another professional, everything organized facilitates the investigation. That's how I see it." LM1 "So, laboratories will be more cautious, making and releasing these results which should be normal. Being cautious should be normal. But this leaves it written eternally and facilitating patient access to this error."</p>	<p>2:17 ¶ 73 in Transcription - Group2 1:49 ¶ 184 in Transcription - Group1 1:43 ¶ 139 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Integration with automated systems	Communication Interoperability	<p>PS2 "There's equipment that already outputs the complete result, right. Maybe you can even integrate it with the medical record. It already sends the information, no need to type anything" LM1 "It sends these results to the interfacing server and the server gets these patient results and sends them to the hospital system. So normally, we don't type the results, okay? So the solution for what you're saying is for it to communicate, obviously, uploading these results to, obviously, after the analyst, the biomedical scientist validates the result, this result automatically uploads to their system."</p>	<p>2:21 ¶ 97 in Transcription - Group2 1:37 ¶ 109 in Transcription - Group1</p>

Lessons learned and opport	Patient access control and the LGPD	Control Access LGPD Emergency Access Privacy	<p>IS2 "Think about this context of Data Protection Law application. Suppose Patient2 hasn't authorized anyone to look at their data, then suddenly they're in emergency, takes dipyrone and has a seizure. I don't have their history because they didn't authorize, I don't know if they had seizures before, if they were allergic to dipyrone. If they're alone, how will I... if the intention is that the patient has their medical record context shared, from primary to tertiary care, if they deny... that someone has access to this, it's clear that if paper dies, I mean actual paper. No one will have access to their history, it will always be the same."</p> <p>IS2 "Just get their chart and verify their hospitalization context. But in electronic form, my understanding is, if they've denied it, the question is that I have access to this data, I'll know they were admitted, but won't have access to past progress notes."</p> <p>Patient2: "But there would be these two points, of them being unconscious and them being conscious but not knowing how to use, not knowing how to work with the technology they have."</p> <p>PS2 "Maybe IT personnel have to provide this access, releasing the password, or somehow, but we need access, because sometimes it's literally about saving someone's life, and there's information that will be fundamental for us to know the history."</p> <p>LM2 "It becomes very difficult for us to have control about the patient and the proper management that needs to be taken, depending on their situation, sometimes it can even hinder or prevent medical autonomy or even the multiprofessional team's autonomy."</p> <p>Patient2 "I believe it's really important that I, Patient2, would leave my medical record pre-released for people... pre-released, you know. And if I didn't want to release it, then I would go there and block it, but I would leave it readily available."</p> <p>LM1 "So we also have to think about another way, right? The patient is having a heart transplant, and they need constant blood gas tests from the laboratory. Okay? To check the patient's condition during surgery. If the system goes down, how will the doctor access this data."</p> <p>LM1 "Regarding privacy, it's perfect, and that's what LGPD asks for, right? Which is precisely the service user having control over their data. I don't know this in any other system, off-the-shelf systems. I don't know any that has this functionality. Normally, anyone who has access today would know IS's results, Patient's... That would be somewhat of an invasion to the patient."</p> <p>IS1 "Now, if the patient wants to deny, they can go in and deny. I thought about that too."</p> <p>PS1 "If the patient wants to have the medical record, which is their right, they can request it from the hospital. They can request, they have access to the medical record, a copy, that's OK. But I rarely saw families requesting it."</p>	<p>2:23 ¶ 109 in Transcription - Group2 2:24 ¶ 109 in Transcription - Group2 2:25 ¶ 111 in Transcription - Group2 2:27 ¶ 123 in Transcription - Group2 2:32 ¶ 143 in Transcription - Group2 2:33 ¶ 169 in Transcription - Group2 1:33 ¶ 91 in Transcription - Group1 1:39 ¶ 121 in Transcription - Group1 1:28 ¶ 79 in Transcription - Group1 1:21 ¶ 63 in Transcription - Group1 1:41 ¶ 127 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Technology adoption barriers.	Emergency Access Professional Engagement	<p>Patient2 "But there would be these two points - them being unconscious and them being conscious but not knowing how to use, not knowing how to work with the technology they have."</p> <p>PS1 "Not every patient will understand this flow because, for example, I have extremely poor patients who don't have access to education, understand? Even for us to explain something minimally, they don't understand. Let alone having an access password, having a medical record, understand? I think this type of tool serves more for a minimally educated patient."</p> <p>IS1 "Besides patients being somewhat lay people, there are also some professionals who have difficulties too."</p> <p>IS1 "So it requires training, requires healthcare team training to use this medical record properly. I think that's it, insert as much information as possible about this patient, the matter of allergies, clinical history is something we have a lot of difficulty with, many times."</p> <p>Patient1 "Obviously, this completely solves this problem, but when you invest in all this solution from a technological point of view, it won't be completely perfect, right."</p>	<p>2:25 ¶ 111 in Transcription - Group2 1:14 ¶ 51 in Transcription - Group1 1:22 ¶ 63 in Transcription - Group1 1:23 ¶ 63 in Transcription - Group1 1:29 ¶ 79 in Transcription - Group1</p>
	Medical care levels.	Improvements	<p>IS1 "I had a doubt about your proposal, about what level of care it would be for"</p> <p>LM1 "Those who periodically go back and forth to the hospital, right? It fits perfectly there"</p> <p>LM2 "That's a point I wanted to make, maybe the use of this PEP in terms of the patient having this autonomy, wouldn't be good in terms of the issue within a health institution, but rather integrating it with other institutions"</p> <p>LM1 "Then you can offer a way for doctors to have"</p> <p>LM1 "So, the patient's entire history will be broken for a period of, I don't know, 10 hours. Or establish a margin there, you would have to look at the legal issue in this. The patient is admitted, the confidentiality is broken and any doctor in that hospital will have access to that patient's data."</p>	<p>1:4 ¶ 7 in Transcription - Group1 1:44 ¶ 139 in Transcription - Group1 2:31 ¶ 143 in Transcription - Group2</p>